

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF LTE-ADVANCED SYSTEMS AND DEVELOPED INTERFERENCE DETECTION MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Landscape features, that affect the route of the line are the most significant part of this research. These features are incorporated into GIS, and using information gathered from stakeholders, the route with minimum opposition is developed between two substations. In this work, a brief introduction is given to the main legal requirements involved in this regard. Non-point impacts that are independent of terrain are also given in detail. To carry out the proposed work, we will measure the radios by not using the instrument used to measure the inaudible noise in the conventional way. With this, we will not acquire cost separately and the available resources will also be used, because different types of RF instruments are better than microphones for measuring radios.

Keywords: RF, GIS, JTCL, Inaudible Noise, PLC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Operators migrating to LTE may deploy their networks in any of the bands assigned e.g., 900MHz, 1800MHz, 700MHz, 2.6GHz etc. with a channel bandwidth of 1.4, 3, 5, 10, 15 and 20 MHz. LTE networks should be backward compatible with the existing systems so as to provide seamless experience to the large base of existing mobile subscribers. LTE-A's benefits are about more than just speed. LTE-A enables smoother "handoffs" when travelling between cells, so that we won't lose our connection so much. And it packs more speed into the same amount of spectrum, which allows more people to access the network at once. In the current age, where everything from cars to slow cookers becomes connected, we're going to need that extra capacity.

Now a days, the continuous increase in the voltage level of transmission lines makes corona discharge problems have become one of the main issues in the development of 4G transmission. In the case of cross-over, the surface field strength of the power line is more difficult to calculate than the ordinary single-circuit line, which makes the prediction of the noise distribution across the transmission lines more complicated [7]. Since the study involves analysis of performance of LTE systems, a heuristic approach has been adopted for the same. A system level simulator tool developed by the networking group of the Telecommunication Research team, called MIS (Management Information System) has been used to emphasize the importance of carrier aggregation and indirect measurement scheme in 4G systems. Scenarios have been designed and simulated using MATLAB to study the effect of the inter site distances, operating frequencies, scheduling algorithms, antenna height and antenna pole spacing on the network performance parameters.

II. BACKGROUND THEORY

Gregory M. Stone et al. [1] has develop guidelines for the design of 800 MHz land-mobile radio communication systems. The design and engineering of land-mobile communications systems in different frequency bands is, in general, quite similar. However, every band requires that certain aspects of the design be given particular attention, because of the peculiarities or special characteristics of that band.

Yokoshima Kato et al. [2] has been presented a method to evaluate the noise temperature of a microwave noise source using three transmission lines to directly measure the temperature correction of the transmission line. Finally, he has suggested that the usefulness of this technique should be verified experimentally.

K. Tanabe et al. [4] environmental problems, especially hum noise near transmission lines, have become a major concern and one of the greatest limiting factors in the design of transmission lines. Some reports have been published with regard to suppression of corona activity on conductor bundles. In this paper he uses 'Random Noise' instead of 'audible noise' because the level of random noise in the component frequency of over 500 Hz is

almost equivalent to the level of audible noise.

Yingyi Liu et al. [8] said that the Audible noise has a serious negative impact on the lives and health of the residents around transmission lines. Therefore, it is very important to detect and study audible noise for the optimal design of transmission lines. At present, the audible noise of transmission lines is obtained by the direct detection method, that is, the sound pressure of audible noise is directly measured by a dedicated device to obtain the sound level and the spectrum. The advantage of this method is convenient and accurate in quiet environments. When conducting audible noise detection, it will inevitably be affected by surrounding background noises. These noises often include sudden disturbance noises such as vehicle driving, passing aircraft, animal calls, wind and so on. Previous studies have shown that these sudden noises belong to broadband noises, which are difficult to be removed from the spectrum of audible noise. Especially when audible noise is relatively small, the error caused by the above background noises is particularly large. Therefore, it is difficult to satisfy the need for accurate measurement of corona audible noise in different background environments.

III. INTERFERENCE MANAGEMENT

LTE systems encounter heavy interference at the cell edges due to the surrounding areas. Lifeng Lai et al. consider the interference detection and resource allocation issue in LTE-U with CA [9]. However, since the two systems have significantly different PHY/MAC protocols, the existence of LTE-U may bring serious implication. He has discussed about the hidden terminal problem in LTE-U deployment, where WiFi APs follow the carrier sense multiple access with collision avoidance (CSMA/CA) mechanism. He has proposed a user interference detection algorithm which utilizes channel quality indicator (CQI) feedback [9]. Joel Fox et al. [9] has predict near field horizontally polarized field strength and far field radiation patterns of signals radiating in the HF band (2 – 30 MHz) from a 2000-foot span of (13kV or less) medium voltage electrical transmission line typical of those used to transport Broadband over Power Lines (BPL) signals. Interference potential to high antenna gain, low noise floor, HF ground side receive sites was analyzed. As is always the case, the more accurate the simulation, the closer the simulation results will come to real-world situations.

C. P. Colvero et al. [6] has presented results of non-intentional irradiation measurements by broadband over power line in medium voltage power line distributions with voice and data transmission in the HF frequencies. Since the first experiments in various countries of the world, focused on proliferation of installation and use of communications systems for voice and data network over electric power lines, called PLC/BPL Systems, there is widespread concern with the issue of spurious generated by the operation of these systems in the frequency range of 1 to 30 MHz. These facts underline the importance in maintaining proper protections against interference and regulations that can ensure proper security for services using HF band.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

There are two measurement approaches: short-term and long-term. These methods are based on the survey and does not so effective. One of the major issues is related to the corona performance of the lines. The traditional approach to performance is based on information and techniques available. The traditional techniques are backward looking. That is, they focus on past performance rather than latest measured experiments. The concern about the limitations of existing performance measurement system has been felt in both theory circles and in most organizations. Performance measures focus more on cost and revenue data and less on the process.

Most of the time it provides irrelevant or misleading information. Performance measures which contain bottom line results are too late to take up useful corrective action. Performance measures are without activity and process analysis which are essential to decide the value-added and non-value-added activity and process. Performance measures are based on tracking single dimensions of performance and they do not provide an integrated or holistic view of performance. Since performance is measured in specific areas only, managers tend to find themselves unable to assess whether they have implemented their strategies effectively. For bigger projects, especially start-up operations, an additional dimension comes into play, and that's capital cost.

Jabalpur Transmission Company Limited (JTCL): Jabalpur Transmission Company Limited (JTCL) was incorporated on September 8, 2009. We believe that the Jabalpur-Dharamjaygarh line of JTCL is India's first 765 KV double circuit line owned by a private company [5, 6]. We have chosen 4 locations to implement our work:

- Avantha Power Plant, Jhabua, Ghansour;
- Mohaans, Jabalpur-Nagpur Road;
- New Mandala Road;
- Rampur Chhaapar.

First of all, we will choose 4 locations in Jabalpur. In each location, we will try to measure by the 4G signal being received in the nearby GSM cell site, where very modern equipment such as Huawei outdoor units are used for measurement. For this, first we will get the distance between the 4G GSM base station subsystem from the transmission line through GIS software.

Fig. 1. Four geographical adverse locations chosen in Jabalpur

Measurements will be made during the day and also at night. The 4G signal is usually broadcast on -70 decibel meter. When the receive signal is prominent at the base station, it is the mixed signal (Gross PSD) of the noise of the area, the noise of the transmission line and the power spectral density of the mobile signal. Interference generated in the 4G signal is measured differently by the base station.

It is generated by the noise in the interference environment. Hence it is displayed by Noise PSD. No signal is transmitted to the transmission line during load shedding. During this time the environmental noise can be measured by the base station. After load shedding, the transmission line's noise can be obtained by subtracting the total noise and the environmental noise. The same method will be implemented at night, so that the effect of temperature, humidity and air flow on the noise of the transmission line can be determined. It has been made clear through various articles that the environmental condition has the opposite effect on this noise.

It is also necessary to analyse some parameters such as the height from the ground of the measuring antenna, and the distance between the towers of the transmission line. Therefore, we have also used these parameters. Finally, all the methods used so far are shown in the Literature, comparing them and the results of the proposed work, so that we know that the proposed method is very important in measuring microwave noise into LTE measurement.

Gonghao Xie et al. analysed the audible noise of the transmission line [7]. The audible noise emitted from high-voltage lines is caused by the discharge of energy that occurs when the electrical field strength on the conductor surface is greater than the 'breakdown strength' (the field intensity necessary to start a flow of electric current) of the air surrounding the conductor. This discharge is also responsible for radio noise, a visible glow of light near the conductor [7].

Noise PSD Measurement through LTE:

1. APIL Power Ltd. Jhabua

Distance: 6000 meters

Measurement at Day time [3]

C₁₁ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) = NA_NL_C₁₁ = -99
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₁ = -29

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₁ = -22

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₁ = -7

Measurement at Night time [3]

C₁₂ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₂ = -110
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₂ = -40

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₂ = -31

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₂ = -9

3. Mangeli New Mandala Road

Distance: 1500 meters

Measurement at Day time [3]

C₁₅ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₅ = -96
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₅ = -26

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₅ = -21

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₅ = -5

Measurement at Night time [3]

C₁₆ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₆ = -103
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₆ = -33

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₆ = -29

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₆ = -4

2. Manegaon Jabalpur-Nagpur Road

Distance: 600 meters

Measurement at Day time [3]

C₁₃ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =

NA_NL_C₁₃ = -97
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₃ = -27

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₃ = -5

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₃ = -6

Measurement at Night time [3]

C₁₄ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₄ = -103
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₄ = -33

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₄ = -28

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₄ = -5

4. Sub-station Nayagaon

Distance: 400 meters

Measurement at Day time [3]

C₁₇ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₇ = -99
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₇ = -29

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₇ = -21

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₇ = -8

Measurement at Night time [3]

C₁₈ = -70
 Area Noise PSD + Line Noise PSD + Mobile Signal PSD =
 Gross PSD (NA+NL+C) =
 NA_NL_C₁₈ = -105
 Noise PSD = NA_NL₁₈ = -35

during load shedding
 Area Noise PSD in dB = NA₁₈ = -28

after load shedding
 Line Noise PSD = NL₁₈ = -7

V. CONCLUSIONS

In the proposed work, we have used the Interference detection model to measure the Inaudible Noise from transmission lines. In order to do something as magical as provide a specific probability for observing a particular mean or a particular difference between two means, our statistical procedures must make some assumptions. We might assume that our data are contained within a particular time-period. These assumptions about the data can be expectations or hopes, conscious or subconscious.

Fig. 2. The Observation Table_1 GUI

In areas where signal reception would normally be strong, other factors can have an effect on reception or may cause complete failure. Poor cell phone signal is a very common problem: the majority of our customers come to Waveform looking for a solution to their own, very specialized, cell signal problems. A common situation is a home or office with few or no signal bars and frequently dropped calls. Whether or not a repeater can help in this situation depends on the cause of the problem - which you the customer can usually determine quite easily. Bad cell phone reception is a ubiquitous problem across the United States, and the causes of bad signal fall under two categories: localized poor coverage due to building materials or destructive interference, and geographical distance from or obstacles between your phone and the nearest cell tower. Interference can be created from the transmission line of the cell site due to intermodulation of its passive elements. This analysis also identifies any interfering signals which may degrade the intended service.

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